

Socio-economic assessment of PAs in Australia

(**PARSEC**: Building New Tools for Data Sharing and
Re-use through a Transnational Investigation of the
Socioeconomic Impacts of Protected Areas)

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PARSEC is a project sponsored by the Belmont Forum as part of its Collaborative Research Action (CRA) on Science-Driven e-Infrastructures Innovation (SEI), with funding from FAPESP, the ANR, JST and the NSF, with collaborators from Australia, and support from the synthesis centre CESAB of the French Foundation for Research on Biodiversity.

We acknowledge the Traditional Owners and Custodians of the land and sea in all nations. We honour their profound connections to land, water, biodiversity and culture and pay our respects to their Elders past, present and emerging.

Protected Areas

NEW
ZEALAND

Protected areas

- Definition of the protected areas

Associated towns

- The associated towns (affected and unaffected) need to be in the same **ecoregion**.

Mirrors

- Counting by the same **ecoregion**
- Socioeconomics and physical variables to match affected and control towns

First cut: associated Towns (82 towns)

Subsequent cut – affected towns - 35

- Ecoregion

Arnhem Land Tropical Savanna
Australian Alps Montane Grasslands
Brigalow Tropical Savanna
Cape York Peninsula Tropical Savanna
Carpentaria Tropical Savanna
Central Ranges Xeric Scrub
Eastern Australian Temperate Forests
Eyre And York Mallee
Jarrah-Karri Forest And Shrublands
Kimberly Tropical Savanna
Murray-Darling Woodlands And Mallee
Naracoorte Woodlands
Pilbara Shrublands
Queensland Tropical Rain Forests
Southeast Australia Temperate Forests
Southwest Australia Savanna
Swan Coastal Plain Scrub and Woodlands
Tasmanian Temperate Forests
Tirari-Sturt Stony Desert

Mirror towns

Variables used to match affected versus control towns

1. Climate: Yearly average of 24 climate variables (1970-2000)
2. Altitude
3. Slope
4. Roughness index
5. Land use from MODIS/ESA (1992- date of creation of PA) (or other)
6. Population at date of PA creation)
7. Annual growth rate (before PA creation)
8. Distance to another selected (M)PA in km
9. Distance to any other protected area in km (terrestrial or marine)
10. Distance to a large city (+20K inhab.) in km

data sources (for this talk)

- Ground truth data
 - Census data (Australian Bureau of Statistics) collected every 5 years: 1996, 2001, 2006, 2011, 2016 etc.
- Remote sensed data
 - Night lights

Night lights for affected towns

Arrows match date of PA creation for the PA next to each town

Census-sourced variables

Mesh
Blocks

- The "building blocks" of the census
- 2016 Census contains 358,122 Mesh Blocks
- Generally follow man-made or natural boundaries (ie. roads, rivers, etc)

SA1s

- Aggregates of Mesh Blocks
- 2016 Census contains 57,523 SA1s
- Generally contain population of 200 - 800 people

SA2s

- Aggregates of SA1s & Mesh Blocks
- 2016 Census contains 2,310 SA2s
- Generally contain population of 3,000 to 25,000 people

SA3s

- Aggregates of SA2s, SA1s & Mesh Blocks
- 2016 Census contains 358 SA3s
- Generally contain population of 30,000 - 130,000 people

SA4s

- Aggregated of SA3s, SA2s, SA1s and Mesh Blocks
- 2016 Census contains 18 SA4s
- Generally contain population of 100,000 - 500,000 people

States and
Territories

- All States and Territories of Australia

■ SA1
 ■ SA2
 ■ SA3
 ■ SA4
 ■ LGA
 ■ GCCS

SA2

Well-being Metrics

- **Longevity (SA4):** Same as that for the Brazilian team (0-1)
- **IRSD (SA1):** The Index of Relative Socio-economic Disadvantage (IRSD: a general socio-economic index that summarises a range of information about the economic and social conditions of people and households within an area. Unlike the other indexes, this index includes only measures of relative disadvantage.
- **IEO(SA1):** The Index of Education and Occupation (IEO): designed to reflect the educational and occupational levels of communities. The education variables in this index show either the level of qualification achieved or whether further education is being undertaken. This index does not include any income variables.
- **Income (SA1):** same as that for the Brazilian team (0-1)

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Thankyou

RESEARCH DATA ALLIANCE

**BELMONT
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